

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 2.9 Practitioners’ Gaps and Requirements – 3rd Publicly available annual report for industry and academia 2024

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1. Summary

This document contains the 3 publicly available reports developed from Work Package 2 practitioner workshops. These reports outline the priorities of Law Enforcement at an operational level, and the opportunities for development across the three topics covered by the workshops:

- Internet of Things (IoT) Devices,
- Investigating Cyber Related Services, and
- Misuse of Virtual Reality Technologies and use of Generative Artificial Intelligence to Generate Child Sexual Abuse Material.

These reports are intended to act as a steer for industry and academia.

2. Internet of Things (IoT) Devices

The term IoT refers to physical objects or “things” and the networking of these physical objects and devices with other devices or systems over the Internet. IoT devices are hardware devices, such as smartphones, smart home devices, wearables, connected cars or smart cities for example. While performing various tasks in our everyday lives, these devices collect, exchange and process a variety of data, including personal information, location data, and communication data.

With the growing number of IoT devices used in our everyday lives, digital forensics plays an important role in extracting and analysing potentially relevant data from IoT devices.

A major challenge for law enforcement agencies is the variety of different IoT devices and their operating systems, as well as the constant and fast evolution and innovations in the field. Each device could have a different operating systems and software versions, making forensic investigation more complex. Forensic experts must therefore build and constantly expand their in-depth knowledge and experience of these different devices and systems.

The IoT Devices workshop brought together expert practitioners from across 8 European countries to discuss Law Enforcement Agencies (LEA) operational use and future requirements for investigations involving IoT devices.

2.1. Priorities of Law Enforcement in the field of IoT devices

There is no standardisation of the data format used in IoT devices. As such, practitioners agreed that developing best practice guides and better knowledge sharing between LEAs is a key priority.

In addition, practitioners highlighted that the data collected from IoT devices is often not stored locally but in a cloud. Cloud service providers are often uncooperative or slow to respond when asked for assistance. Better cooperation from cloud service providers was therefore also listed as a key priority.

2.2. Opportunities for development within IoT Devices

- **Multipurpose tooling**

Currently, each IoT device typically needs to be investigated using a number of different techniques and tools. Practitioners agreed that multi-purpose tooling and hardware which would work on a number of IoT device types.

- **Ability to visualise data across different devices**

Data visualisation tools which have the capability to correlate data between different IoT devices and visualise it would assist with investigations.

- **Training for IoT devices**

More training in respect of IoT devices at all levels – from the frontline officers to the digital forensics investigators right through to the prosecutors and judiciary.

- **Platform/channel for LEAs to exchange information on IoT devices**

Often, the starting point for an investigator when they need to analyse an IoT device is 'have I come across this device in the past' and if not 'has anyone else?'. An online platform/channel for LEAs to exchange information on IoT devices would be beneficial.

- **Location of data stored on IoT device**

At a crime scene, investigators need to be able to quickly identify where the data is stored – whether it is stored locally, on a mobile device or in the Cloud. Tools, training and best practice could assist.

- **Data privacy and data protection**

More tools and best practice guidance which would allow for the selective extraction and prevent collateral intrusion could prevent an unnecessary incursion into people's privacy.

3. Investigating Cybercrime Related Services

This practitioner workshop focused on the investigation of Cybercrime affecting systems and networks, which are committed through the use of online devices, such as a computer, computer networks or other forms of information communications technology (ICT). These online devices are both the tool for committing the crime, and the target of the crime; for example, generating and spreading malware for financial gain and hacking to compromise data, computer networks or activity.

Cyber-attacks are challenging to investigate and often consist of multiple steps, with multiple threat actors, working on different parts of the 'crime-as-a-service' process. LEA need to work with individuals, public and private sector organisations to secure and recover evidence to support judicial proceedings, however this can often be challenging due to the complex nature of cyber-attacks and the skills and experience of IT professionals and LEA specialist practitioners.

LEA investigations need to understand and exhibit the following:

- how a computer system and/or network has been compromised to gain unauthorised access, e.g., vulnerability exploited.
- what malicious program or code has been installed on the asset and what is it doing, e.g., rootkit, fake antivirus, or spyware.
- How the attacker(s) are communicating with the compromised devices, e.g., identity of the Command & Control centre.

The CYCLOPES practitioner workshop on Investigating Cybercrime Related Services provided an opportunity and platform for LEAs to discuss how to respond to these incidents, how they cooperate with public and private sector organisations and what evidence can be gathered from the compromised computer system and network server logs.

3.1. Priorities of Law Enforcement in the field of Investigating Cybercrime Related Services

Practitioners suggested that developing comprehensive legal frameworks for crypto asset management is a key priority. Improved tools to trace cryptocurrency transactions that utilise obfuscation methods such as mixers were also highlighted.

In addition, practitioners highlighted the priorities of developing a framework to facilitate cooperation with Law Enforcement from Cryptocurrency exchanges and services; establishing a centralised repository to assist with cryptocurrency address attribution; improving links between LEAs and academic institutions; improved automated tools for standard cryptocurrency transactions.

3.2. Opportunities for development within investigations involving Cybercrime Related Services

- **High Volume of Data**

Typically, during an investigation of this type, large volumes of data is collected, and this can present a number of challenges. More solutions are needed to analyse and triage this data and to automate some of the burdensome manual tasks.

- **Dark Web Crawler at a European level**

Currently, dark web crawlers are typically maintained by individual LEAs. It was agreed that it could be beneficial for there to be just one European dark web crawler that was maintained by one central European agency.

- **A User Education Platform**

It can require a lot of time to train a cyber investigator and the turnover of staff is high as they develop a valuable skillset. A user-education platform which could assist with training would be of benefit to LEAs.

- **A Standard Data Model to be used by all Law Enforcement Agencies**

In addition to the provision of more open-source software, it would assist investigations if a standard data model was used throughout Europe.

- **More Open-Source Alternatives to Commercial Software**

Many of the licenses for commercial software are expensive. As cybercrime is a crime that often transcends borders it is beneficial to everyone for all countries to have access to the software that is needed to combat these crime types.

- **Better Sharing of Technical Knowledge**

The expertise/knowledge of cyber criminals is ever evolving. For LEAs to keep up to date it is imperative that intelligence and technical knowledge is better shared between LEAs. Tools and channels that would enable seamless international collaboration are needed.

4. The Misuse of Virtual Reality Technologies and Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence to Generate Child Sexual Abuse Material

Over recent years the use of VR headsets has grown in popularity amongst children. As the technology becomes cheaper and more mainstream, one of the disadvantages has been the significant increased uptake of this technology by offenders that are misusing VR spaces to abuse and harm children. VR spaces that particularly appeal to young people are being used by offenders focused on grooming children, with the aim to move them to private chat rooms once a rapport has been established. Another example of advanced technology being utilised by offenders is generative artificial intelligence (GAI) applications that can create images from user text prompts.

A major challenge for LEAs is the scale that new material can be produced, its realism and difficulty to distinguish from genuine photographs. It is vital that LEAs can identify victims quickly, however GAI can create a forest of images quickly making it far more difficult to identify images of real abuse and therefore identify and safeguard victims quickly.

VR and GAI is amplifying pre-existing Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation (CSAE) risks. Policy and legislation in particular, play an important role as technology evolves at a constant and rapid pace, and its interpretation and application to CSAE offences that take place in VR spaces, involve GAI Child Sexual Abuse Material (CSAM), or both, will impact on the outcomes of police investigations. Therefore, it is essential that police investigators, digital forensic practitioners, policy makers and legislators have the necessary expertise and tools to conduct effective investigations.

4.1. Priorities of Law Enforcement in the field of the Misuse of Virtual Reality Technologies and Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence to Generate Child Sexual Abuse Material

The foundation of effective digital crime investigation lies in the ability to access and analyse data, which continues to be a priority issue for LEAs due to dealing with encrypted, erased, and cloud-stored data.

Offenders know how to exploit technical loopholes to their advantage and practitioners agreed action is needed to better protect individuals from exploitation and harm leading from the conditioning of VR and GAI environments.

In addition, focusing on victims and raising public awareness are essential components of combating digital crimes. Comprehensive support systems for victims of digital crimes need to be developed along with targeted safety awareness campaigns.

Collaboration and unified approach amongst LEAs and various stakeholders to share learning and pool resources would assist with resource constraints.

Inconsistent data retention policies and access rights hinder evidence collection and case compilation. Amongst the different European countries, the data retention times vary from 7 days to 2 years. Practitioners agreed harmonized data retention laws that balance privacy concerns with investigative needs would be highly beneficial.

4.2. Opportunities for development within investigations involving the Misuse of Virtual Reality Technologies and Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence to Generate Child Sexual Abuse Material

- **The development of sophisticated forensic tools for VR and GAI content detection**
- **Improved mechanisms for victim identification and origin source material**

Large volumes of data can be created for use in this type of crime and environment, which presents a number of challenges, the most important for LEAs being able to quickly identify victims. More solutions are needed to analyse and triage this data and to automate some of the manual tasks.

- **Collaboration with tech companies to incorporate educational tools and resources into platforms**
- **Developing parental and school awareness programs on digital safety**

- **Partner with private and third sectors for comprehensive awareness campaigns**

Raising awareness and engaging the community are essential for preventive measures, especially as the technology evolves as a rapid pace.

- **Cooperation from ISPs and tech companies in investigations through legislative support and partnerships**
- **The development of triage and case management systems to expedite evidence processing**

The challenges with large volumes of data also impact on evidence gathering and analysis. Establishing clear guidelines for lawful access to digital content, including cloud storage under investigation, would significantly help speed up investigations and therefore better support victims. In addition to this, the development of international agreements to facilitate cross-border digital investigations and evidence sharing would assist with timely prosecutions.